

Law Impact in Software Development in European Union

Alinur Mammadzada^{1*} & Mahammad Aliyev¹

¹Department of Computer Engineering, Vistula University, Warsaw, Poland

* Corresponding Author: Alinur Mammadzada, Email: amammad9@stu.vistula.edu.pl

APA Citation and Referencing: Alinur, M., & Mahammad, A. (2025). Law Impact in Software Development in European Union. *JENER Journal of Empirical and Non-Empirical Research*, 1(3), 275-280

ARTICLE INFORMATION	ABSTRACT
<p>Article history: Published on 26TH Nov 2025</p> <p>Keywords: European Union GDPR DORA Software Development Digital Decade</p>	<p>The study analyzes the impact of the EU legislation, specifically the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and the Digital Operational Resilience Act (DORA), on software development processes and innovations. Using an analytical approach, the research examines how these regulations shape software development in different stages of lifecycle. The analysis reveals that GDPR affects the early stages, protection of data and user-privacy. Moreover, the findings show several statistics about the companies. So that 80% of companies are not yet ready to be fully compliant, and 73% of companies have not yet started the compliance processes. As a result, the cost of fines is increasing. According to statistics, the cost of fines is nearly €1 254 684 666 to companies for not obeying the GDPR regulations. This links that companies are not fully ready to be compliant with regulations. On the other hand, DORA mainly focuses on post-deployment processes withing financial organizations. While these regulations increase costs, they create a secure, transparent, and sustainable digital world. Altogether, GDPR and DORA complete each other and help the EU achieve the goal for a safe digital ecosystem.</p>

1. Introduction

Software development has brought a big revolution in our lives. People can perform all their activities such as sending money, talking with friends, and learning new topics, with applications. For instance, WhatsApp (Communication Platform) is used actively by nearly 3 billion people, and Nubank (Digital Banking) reached 120 million customers [1][2]. This statistic shows that software applications are a huge part of our life. While this shows how important software applications are, we need to first know what software development is. People think software development is only about coding. However, software development is the combination of multiple complex phases such as analyzing, designing, coding, testing, etc. These phases combine and bring a software application. While software applications are very useful among people, there are several problems that concern people. The data protection or the general security of the application can worry people as these applications have our data and even our bank accounts. Moreover, users did not know about the development processes of the applications. People may think that companies are collecting their data and selling it to third-party organizations. All these concerns lead European Union law to take control of software development and apply new legislation, which will make the development process safer. In 2022, the EU decided to launch a new program called “Digital Decade” [3]. This program’s aims are to create a much safer digital environment and make people count on the digital environment. One of the goals of “Digital Decade” is to regulate software development [10]. This goal aimed to put pressure on companies and protect the data of the users. This was an important step because companies started to pay attention to their projects, documentations, and all other processes. One of the ways to do that is GDPR regulations. This paper aims to analyze the legislation which the EU wants the companies to obey, and how they affect the companies. The legislation can affect the progress of innovations in software development. So, we are going to analyze how these laws will affect the innovations that may happen in software development.

2. Methodology

2.1 Research Design

This study follows an analytical design. During the analysis, this research focuses on GDPR (General Data Protection Regulation) and DORA (Digital Operational Resilience Act), and how they affect innovations and processes in software development. The research is based on analysis of legal documents and technical sources. Moreover, this paper investigates laws and academic sources to dig into both technical and theoretical parts of software development. So, multiple perspectives are considered to understand European legislation and how they affect developers, procedures, and documentation in the software industry. The

research focuses on the period between 2015-2025 and studying the changes in EU law and its effect on developers. The methodology design allows for understanding the connection between law and software development processes.

2.2 Data and Source of Data

The study materials and data are collected from official and academic sources. The main materials include the EU laws about the General Data Protection Regulation and Digital Services Act. Additional materials are from research from peer reviewed academic journals in Google Scholar, master's thesis from University of Turku [3], and publications from European universities. Sources were selected according to their publication time, and relevancy with software development and European laws.

2.3 Theoretical Approach

Until the European Union took control, product standards were decided by the countries [8]. For that reason, there were problems between legislation and producers. These problems needed to be solved, but there was a balance needed for that. Thus, there will be no problem between the companies and the laws. At the same time, there will be innovations in software development [9]. The EU aimed to lessen the problems. Therefore, they decided to launch a program called "Digital Decade" in 2022 [3]. The aim of this program was to create a secure digital environment by 2030, which will protect both human and company rights. With the launch of the program GDPR and DORA legislations were introduced to create a strong privacy and security in the software development industry [5] [7].

GDPR (General Data Protection Regulation) is a legal framework that deals with data processing and data transferring. The main purpose of this regulation is to protect the users' private data and provide their rights. The data processing processes prove this purpose. So that when the data controller tries to process user's data, s/he needs to provide the purpose and period of data processing. Also, this process includes the agreement on automated decision making. Therefore, data controllers can use user data [5, chapter 3, Article 13]. At the same time, when the user wants to correct or remove personal data, the data controller must obey that and complete the user's request [5, chapter 3, Article 17]. Although GDPR deals mainly with data processing, it also interferes with the development process of software applications. While companies design software projects, they need to make sure that every system that uses personal data should make it a priority. In addition, developers should make sure that in case of failure, there is enough functionality to log the processes before the failure (GDPR DR1) [5, Chapter 4, Article 24]. Also, the data controller must do assessments if there is a risk in data processing. Consequently, data controllers must explain the purpose of data processing and operations. Finally, GDPR declares that there needs to be a supervisory authority for data controllers. Moreover, the EU also planned to make data transfer processes straightforward. Thus, any countries from the EU can transfer data across the EU countries without any legal problems [5, Chapter 1, Article 1]. For instance, when data should be transferred to France from Germany, GDPR provides standards that make processes simpler. Basically, GDPR helps the EU members to not deal with data regulations on their own. Instead, one regulation would solve the problem of 27 countries. DORA (Digital Operational Resilience Act) is another regulation of the EU that deals with IT security of financial organizations. It has been applied since 17 January 2025. DORA aims to make financial organizations build and review their operations' reliability. Nowadays, IT systems can be complex, which can make them vulnerable to cyber-attacks [5]. DORA states that organizations should have enough strategies and procedures to protect information assets. According to DORA regulation, when an incident happens, financial organizations should start a process to detect and manage the process. Moreover, this process should be recorded. For security purposes, the organizations must do penetration tests every 3 years [7].

2.4 Analytical Approach

To systematically answer the research questions, what are the effects of new EU regulations (mainly GDPR) in Software Development practices? And how can such changes be made? hybrid approach consisting of a Regulatory Content Analysis, and Comparative Requirements Mapping. The analysis analyzes important laws like GDPR and DORA and uses a page-by-page method to figure out legislation that affects software development [5][7].

This analysis will focus on multiple aspects of software development, such as the financial aspects (FA), software developer challenges (SDC), and GDPR compliance and awareness (CA). The financial aspect analyzes the financial costs that the GDPR regulations cost to the EU countries and software companies. The SDC is about challenges such as lack of familiarity or resources that happen to software developers and companies. The aspect examines the main problems that might cause software developers to face problems with the GDPR regulations. Finally, the CA about how much the companies are considering themselves compliant to the GDPR regulations [11]. It serves as a percentage counter for assessing the current state of regulatory adoption to GDPR requirements. After the content analysis, we'll perform a comparative mapping. The goal here is to draw connections between DORA and aspects that we already know from GDPR [5][7]. This mapping exercise has two main purposes. The first purpose is identifying overlaps and synergies. We need to determine where DORA has requirements that mirror the "good practices" and technical measures we already have from GDPR (like how "Data Protection by Design" is kind of a template for

"Security/Resilience by Design"). The second purpose is to assess organizational adjustment. By classifying aspects such as FA, SDC, or CA, the study can better isolate the burden.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1 Overview

This section focuses on the results of content analysis and figures and tables about the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and Digital Operational Resilience Act (DORA). The analysis examines how different aspects affect software development practices and software development innovations. Data, which is found during analysis, is illustrated through tables and figures and organized based on requirements and their impacts on different stages of the software development process.

3.2 Results from Regulatory Content Analysis

The analysis results show that GDPR mainly focuses on the early stages of software development. Design and testing phases are the main parts of GDPR, which focuses on user data protection and privacy concerns. Conversely, the DORA focuses on other parts in the end, such as operational and maintenance phases. These phases focus on system resilience, cybersecurity, and monitoring. Figure 3.1 focuses on the effects of GPDR on financial aspects. The table analyzes how much does it costs for the EU countries to not obey the GDPR regulations effectively. Then we are going to draw a connection between the financial aspects and challenges the companies face.

Figure 3.1: GDPR Financial Aspect [12]

The analysis of GDPR financial aspect focuses on the fines that the countries get because of not obeying the regulations. According to calculations, the total amount of fines the European countries needed to pay was €1 254 684 666. The top countries in this table are Ireland, Netherlands, and Italy. This shows that countries and companies are still struggling to obey the regulations and protect data privacy accurately. According to EDPB, several measures are taken, such as warning companies about obeying the GDPR regulations, before the countries are fined.

Figure 3.2: GDPR Software Development Challenges with Number of Respondents [11]

Figure 3.3: GDPR Software Development Challenges with percentage [11]

The analysis of the GDPR SDC aspect analyzes certain problems that companies and software developers lack. According to Figure 3.2 and 3.3, Developers are mainly suffering from the familiarity with GDPR. 85% of the responders face the familiarity problem with GDPR regulations. Lack of resources and guidelines is also a problem among developers. So, developers cannot find enough resources to guide themselves to GDPR regulations. Figures 3.3 show that 80% of respondents have a problem with that. Another problem that developers are facing is not being familiar with the techniques to solve problems with GDPR. 70% of responders are facing problems with techniques. Moreover, some developers are not even familiar with any data laws. The statistics show that this may cause several problems for companies as 55% of responders are not familiar with any data laws.

Figure 3.4: Are the companies fully compliant? [11]

Figure 3.5: Have the companies started the compliance process? [11]

Figures 3.4 and 3.5 analyze Compliance and Awareness. The focus is about whether companies started compliance processes. According to figure 3.4, only 20% of companies consider themselves fully compliant to GDPR regulations. This also shows that 80% of companies are not yet ready to be fully compliant. On the other hand, 73% of companies have not yet started compliance processes, which is a very high percentage. In the end, the statistics show that developers are lacking enough knowledge about data protection. As a result, companies and countries are facing serious problems. As the percentage goes high in problems that software developers are facing, the fines are also increasing. Moreover, a vast percentage of companies are lacking the ability to start compliance processes, which also leads to fines and bans in the end.

3.3 Comparative Mapping

The comparison between GDPR and DORA regulations leads us to understand that both regulations are created for increasing transparency and security in digital operations across the European Union. While GDPR focuses on personal data and user privacy protection in software design and development phases, the DORA regulation focuses on operational resilience of financial organizations after the deployment phase. Both regulations are structured for continuous documentation, monitoring, and compliance. In the end, GDPR's personal data and user privacy protection aligns with DORA's resilience, which leads the EU to create a secure digital world and achieve the plan for a much better digital world.

3.4 Innovation Impact Assessment

The results indicate that EU regulations such as GDPR influence innovations. As these regulations require strict documentation, monitoring, and resilience, the costs for software development can initially increase. However, the report from official documents marks that these regulations are designed for the creation of privacy and security enhancing technologies. Therefore, GDPR and DORA support safer and transparent development across the EU's software industry, promoting sustainable innovation with ethical and legal standards.

4. Conclusion

This research analyzed the effects of EU regulations, such as GDPR and DORA, on software development and operational practices. The results indicate that the GDPR mainly influences the early stages of software development, such as the design phase. User privacy and data protection are the main concerns of GDPR, which are planned in the early stages of development. Moreover, different aspects of GDPR, such as financial problems (FA) and developer knowledge problems (SDC) and Compliance problems (CA) are analyzed and visualized in figures. The results show that there are developers that lack knowledge

of GDPR regulations. According to the results, 80% of companies are not ready to be fully compliant, which means that only 20% is ready for that. Furthermore, 73% of companies have not started compliance processes yet. These problems may increase the cost of fines, which is already high. According to statistics, the total cost of fines that connects to GDPR is €1 254 684 666 in 2024. Italy, Netherlands, and Ireland are the most fined countries in 2024. On the other hand, DORA focuses on processes in maintenance and post-deployment in financial organizations. Despite the increases in problems and costs, with documentation and compliance, these regulations focus on a secure, transparent, and resilient digital world across the European Union.

References

- [1] WhatsApp. (2025). About WhatsApp. Retrieved November 13, 2025, from <https://www.whatsapp.com/about>
- [2] Nubank. (2025). About Nu. Retrieved November 13, 2025, from <https://international.nubank.com.br/about/>
- [3] Tynys, E. (2025). *The effects of recent EU regulations on software development* (Master's Thesis). University of Turku, Department of Computing.
- [4] EU Legal Document (Digital Decade) European Parliament and Council of the European Union. (2022). Decision (EU) 2022/2481 of 14 December 2022 establishing the Digital Decade Policy Programme 2030. *Official Journal of the European Union*, L 323/4.
- [5] EU Legal Document (GDPR) European Parliament and Council of the European Union. (2016). Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC (General Data Protection Regulation). *Official Journal of the European Union*, L 119.
- [6] EU Legal Document (AI Act) European Parliament and Council of the European Union. (2024). Regulation (EU) 2024/1689 of 13 June 2024 laying down harmonised rules on artificial intelligence and amending regulations (EC) No 300/2008, (EU) No 167/2013, (EU) No 168/2013, (EU) 2018/858, (EU) 2018/1139 and (EU) 2019/2144 and directives 2014/90/eu, (EU) 2016/797 and (EU) 2020/1828 (Artificial Intelligence Act). *Official Journal of the European Union*, L 2024/1689.
- [7] EU Legal Document (DORA) European Parliament and Council of the European Union. (2022). Regulation (EU) 2022/2554 of 14 December 2022 on digital operational resilience for the financial sector and amending regulations (EC) No 1060/2009, (EU) No 648/2012, (EU) No 600/2014, (EU) No 909/2014 and (EU) 2016/1011. *Official Journal of the European Union*, L 333.
- [8] J. Winn and N. Jondet, "A "new approach" to standards and consumer protection", *Journal of consumer policy*, vol. 31, pp. 459–472, 2008.
- [9] P. G. Chiara, "The IoT and the new EU cybersecurity regulatory landscape", *International Review of Law, Computers & Technology*, vol. 36, no. 2, pp. 118–137, 2022. doi: 10.1080/13600869.2022.2060468.
- [10] Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing directive 95/46/EC (General Data Protection Regulation)", *Official Journal of the European Union*, pp. 1–88, L 119 2016
- [11] Klar, M. (2020). Binding effects of the European General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) on U.S. companies. *UC Law Science and Technology Journal*, 11(2), 101–157.
- [12] European Data Protection Board. (2025). Annual Report 2024. Retrieved from https://www.edpb.europa.eu/system/files/2025-04/edpb-annual-report-2024_en.pdf